

Genetic resources of GEB24

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GEB24, also called Kitchili Samba, selected from the Andhra Pradesh local variety Konamani, was released in 1921. It is tall (120-135 cm), has 150-d duration, and is highly photoperiod sensitive. It tillers profusely, with nonshattering grain. Despite its relatively low yield potential (3.5 t/ha), it is popular mainly for its very good quality rice. Its grain is medium slender and white.

GEB24 has been used extensively in several national and international breeding programs and several modern high-yielding varieties carry its genes.

It is the ultimate maternal progenitor of 18 varieties (see figure). Eight varieties released between 1945 and 1975 are direct derivatives: TKM6 is resistant to stem borer (SB); Co 30 is resistant to blast; co 31 (the fit outcome of interspecific cross) is resistant to drought. Ten varieties released between 1970 and 1983 are second-generation derivatives: Ratna is noted for SB resistance and Punjab Basmati 1, for scented rice.

Derivatives with GEB24 as maternal progenitor.

A list of 83 varieties with GEB24 features inherited paternally is available from the authors. They include 23 from

Tamil Nadu, 20 from other Indian states, 28 from IRRI, and 12 from other countries. □

Masuli, most popular rice variety in Nepal

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Rice in Nepal occupies 59% of the total cultivated land and contributes 52% of the total edible food grain. Rice employs more than 75% of the population (17.5 million) at least 6 mo a year and contributes 23% of the total gross domestic product (GDP).

In 1987, the total rice area was 1.4 million ha, production was 3 million t, with average yield of 2.1 t/ha (see table).

Of the 31 improved rice varieties

Area, production, and productivity of rice in different ecological regions of Nepal in 1987 (Food and Agricultural Marketing Department, Lalitpur, Nepal, 1988).

Ecological region	Area		Production		Productivity (t/ha)
	ha	%	ha	%	
Tarai	1,049,900	73.7	2,249,090	75.2	2.1
Mid-hill	337,890	23.8	667,390	22.3	2.0
High hill	35,500	2.5	65,300	2.5	1.8
Total	1,423,290	100.0	2,981,340	100.0	2.1

(national average)

Nepal has released during the last 20 yr, Masuli, released in 1973, is the most popular in the subtropical climatic region of Tarai, inner Tarai, and similar climatic river basin areas and valleys up to 900-m altitude. In 1987, more than

50% of the total ricelands were planted to improved varieties; Masuli covered 26.6% of the total, more than 379,506 ha. Market surveys indicate that at least 60% of the milled rice marketed in the country is Masuli.

Masuli characteristics are the following:

1. Higher grain yield under low-to-medium fertility.
2. Equally good yield under rainfed lowland.
3. Higher grain yield with late planting condition, even with 60-d-old seedlings.
4. Early maturity (within Nov), leaving time for farmers to plant winter crops.

5. Medium fine, soft, moist cooked grain quality accepted at almost all levels of society.
6. Intermediate tall, giving farmers straw for their cattle.
7. A 15-20% higher market price.
8. More than 32% head rice recovery.

Masuli has become susceptible to blast, particularly at the seedling stage. The fungicide carbendazim is used for its control. □

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Seed technology

Variability in rice seed vigor after storage

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We evaluated 21 shortduration rices with 3 different grain characteristics—long slender, short bold, and medium bold—for germinability after 9 mo storage in 1986-87. Details on seed viability, germination percentage, coleoptile seedling length, vigor index (germination percentage × seedling length), and dry matter production are given in the table.

The medium bold seed type cultivars had higher values for coleoptile length, seedling length, vigor index, and dry matter production than long slender types. Intragroup variability for the physiological parameters was relatively higher than intergroup variability. Intragroup variability was highest in long slender genotypes, followed by the short bold. Medium bold genotypes had the least variability.

Variability in germination and dehydrogenase enzyme activity was considerably higher in long slender genotypes than in medium bold genotypes. The higher dehydrogenase enzyme activity indicates the potential vigor of stored seeds of medium bold genotypes. □

Germination of seeds of 3 genotypes after 9-mo storage, Coimbatore, India.

Genotypes	Germination (%)		Coleoptile length (cm)	Seedling length (cm)		Vigor index	Dry matter production (mg)	Dehydrogenase activity (O.D.)
	Initial	After storage		Initial	After storage			
<i>Long slender</i>								
T2978	100	94	2.15	41.8	35.4	3302	0.0151	0.062
T2021	95	46	1.02	40.0	32.9	1547	0.0087	0.037
T1724	100	85	2.00	40.7	32.4	2771	0.0132	0.115
HY68	95	77	1.92	37.2	32.6	2521	0.0119	0.152
T2023	95	93	1.60	37.0	30.5	2847	0.0118	0.067
T358	100	89	1.50	40.7	34.2	3059	0.0152	0.067
T1814	96	84	2.37	44.1	36.9	3105	0.0132	0.155
Mean	97	83	1.79	40.0	33.5	2736	0.0127	0.093
<i>Short bold</i>								
T1727	100	74	1.70	38.4	30.9	2273	0.0146	0.075
T1406	100	74	1.57	42.4	36.2	3432	0.0179	0.142
T2952	100	97	1.70	38.7	32.8	3153	0.0185	0.087
T1769	95	82	1.40	47.5	35.3	2919	0.0214	0.125
T2006	95	93	3.29	40.7	34.1	3118	0.0169	0.127
T218	92	79	1.92	34.6	29.5	2345	0.0101	0.082
T2099	100	85	2.17	37.5	32.8	2804	0.0156	0.127
Mean	97	88	1.96	40.0	33.0	2863	0.0164	0.109
<i>Medium bold</i>								
T828	100	90	2.65	43.1	40.5	3674	0.0151	0.087
T1668	100	88	2.82	44.5	40.3	3558	0.0176	0.092
T1824	100	87	3.17	42.7	33.9	2943	0.0155	0.115
T2297	96	84	2.50	41.5	35.8	3001	0.0181	0.097
T2832	100	96	2.65	47.9	33.6	3189	0.0153	0.082
SLO 7	100	93	2.75	37.0	35.1	3278	0.0158	0.137
T1704	100	88	2.45	44.5	37.2	3330	0.0175	0.145
Mean	99	90	2.71	43.0	36.6	3281	0.0164	0.107
LSD (0.05)		9.4	0.69		2.8	443	0.0017	0.011
(0.01)		13.0	0.94		3.9	604	0.0024	0.015
Length (mm) × Width (mm)								
Long slender		7.2	×		1.6			
			to					
		8.9	×		1.6			
Short bold		4.1	×		1.8			
			to					
		6.4	×		1.8			
Medium bold		6.6	×		1.9			
			to					
		8.1	×		1.9			